

ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY OF THORIUM. PART IX. DELAYED PRECIPITATION OR PRECIPITATION FROM HOMOGENEOUS SOLUTION

BY C. LAKSHMAN RAO, M. VENKATARAMANIAN AND BH. S. V. RAGHAVA RAO

Two new reagents for the estimation of thorium and its separation from cerite earths have been described. One, ammonium picrate, precipitates thorium completely in the p_H range 4.8 to 5.2 on heating for about 15 minutes on a boiling water-bath. This precipitation takes place gradually during heating and exhibits a behaviour similar to that of precipitation from homogeneous solution studied by Willard and co-workers. The second reagent, ammonium salt of 2:4-dinitrophenol functions satisfactorily in the p_H range 4.8 to 5.2. Thorium in monazite has been successfully estimated employing both reagents.

With few exceptions (oxalic acid, iodic acid), all reagents for thorium give flocculent precipitates, which present some difficulty in filtering and washing. A precipitate, though flocculent, when formed slowly, is more dense, carries less of the mother-liquor and is less difficult to further purify by washing. Slow precipitation, hydrolytic or otherwise, at higher temperatures has of course its disadvantages, particularly the formation of an adherent film of the hydrous oxide or the basic salt which a policeman cannot disengage but requires more drastic treatment with acids. The technique has, however, engaged attention and has yielded valuable results in the hands of Willard and his co-workers (*Anal. Chem.*, 1948, 20, 165). The precipitation of thorium by ammonium picrate partakes of some of these characteristics.

Picric acid was first employed by Speter (*Cont. Met. Chem. Eng.*, 1926, 1, 83) for the estimation of zirconium. Metzger (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 24, 901) investigated the applicability of the reagent to thorium and found it unsuitable. The high strength of the acid probably stands in the way of the precipitation of the thorium salt, for, when the acid is neutralised with ammonia or ammonium picrate is employed, partial precipitation occurs. Thus, when ammonium picrate is added to a neutral or very slightly acid solution (Congo red) of thorium nitrate a coarse precipitate results, but the thorium recovery is only 70% or thereabout. If further ammonium acetate is present in solution, there is no precipitation in the cold. As the temperature is raised (on a water-bath), slow precipitation begins and is complete after 15 minutes over a vigorously boiling water-bath. The precipitate is dense and settles rapidly.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ammonium Picrate

Ammonium picrate was prepared by repeated evaporation on a water-bath of picric acid with silica-free ammonia and crystallisation of the product twice from water.

Precipitation of Thorium: Procedure (I).—The thorium solution was neutralised to Congo red indicator, diluted to about 100 ml. and the p_H of the liquid was adjusted to 4.8 to 5.2 with 10% ammonium acetate solution. To this were next added 100 ml. of a cold 1% solution of ammonium picrate and the mixture heated on a boiling water-

bath for about 20 minutes during which all the thorium was precipitated. The precipitate was then allowed to settle, filtered through a Whatman No. 42 filter, washed with a cold 0.1% solution of the reagent, ignited and weighed as ThO_2 .

The amount of ThO_2 recovered by this means is low by nearly 2 mg. $\bar{3}$ The thorium precipitate forms an adherent film, which is invisible, on the sides and bottom of the beaker. This can be recovered only by treatment with hot 1:1 hydrochloric acid and precipitation with ammonia. During the acid treatment, however, some silica (less than 1 mg.) from the beaker gets into solution and is precipitated by ammonia. The thorium thus recovered needs further treatment with HF and H_2SO_4 to render it silica-free.

Procedure (II): Recovery of Thorium from the beaker.—To the beaker after removal of the thorium precipitate were added 10 ml. of concentrated hydrochloric acid and heated over a small flame for 5 minutes. The beaker was covered with a watch glass to minimise evaporation. On cooling, redistilled ammonia was added until neutral to Methyl red indicator. The precipitate formed was filtered through a small filter, washed, and ignited. The ignited residue on cooling was moistened with 3 to 4 drops of HF and 4 drops of concentrated sulphuric acid, heated first slowly and then ignited strongly. The weight of the residue was added to that of the original oxide.

The results are shown in Table I. In a few cases the minor thorium residue was weighed prior to HF- H_2SO_4 treatment to form an idea of the amount of silica detached from the beaker. These results are shown in Table I A.

TABLE I

No.	ThO_2 taken.	ThO_2 weighed		Total.
		Major fraction.	Minor fraction.	
1	0.0696 g.	0.0678 g.	0.0016 g.	0.0694g.
2	0.0696	0.0682	0.0017	0.0699
3	0.0696	0.0679	0.0017	0.0696
4	0.0696	0.0677	0.0018	0.0695
5	0.0696	0.0683	0.0013	0.0696
6	0.0696	0.0680	0.0015	0.0695

TABLE I A

Silica extracted from the beaker.

No.	ThO_2 taken.	Wt. of minor fraction of ThO_2 (impure).	Wt. of ThO_2 after removal of SiO_2 .	Wt. of silica.
1	0.0696 g.	0.0030 g.	0.0018 g.	0.0012 mg.
2	0.0696	0.0024	0.0016	0.0008
3	0.0696	0.0027	0.0015	0.0012
4	0.0696	0.0024	0.0013	0.0011

Separation of Thorium from Cerite Earths.—Thorium may be freed from the cerite earths with the aid of this reagent. When precipitated as above, small quantities of the cerite earths are carried by thorium, which are, however, removed in a second precipitation.

Double Precipitation.—The precipitate of thorium picrate was transferred along with the filter to the original beaker and digested with 20 ml. of hot 1:1 hydrochloric acid; the filter was macerated, and the excess acid neutralised with ammonia to Congo red. After dilution to 100 ml. the p_H of the liquid was adjusted to 4.8 to 5.2 with 10% ammonium acetate solution, and precipitation of thorium was then repeated. After removing the precipitate, the thoria sticking to the beaker was treated as described earlier and its weight added to that of the main thoria. Results obtained in this way are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	ThO ₂ taken.	R ₂ O ₃ added.	ThO ₂ obtained.	Diff.
1	0.0696 g.	0.1480 g.	0.0694 g.	-0.2 mg.
2	0.0696	0.2960	0.0697	+0.1
3	0.0696	0.5920	0.0696	—
4	0.0348	0.1440	0.0350	+0.2
5	0.0139	0.1480	0.0140	+0.1
6	0.0139	0.2220	0.0140	+0.1

Estimation of Thorium in Monazite.—Thorium in monazite was estimated after a double precipitation from phosphate-free extract of a sample from Travancore (cf. this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 456). In Table III are recorded results of 4 such estimations along with two made with *m*-nitrobenzoic acid (Neish, *Chem. News*, 1904, 90, 196).

TABLE III.

Wt. of sample	% ThO ₂ obtained.	
	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid.	Ammonium picrate.
1.0024 g.	8.24	—
0.9940	8.20	—
0.9910	—	8.25
0.9828	—	8.21
0.9980	—	8.19
1.0180	—	8.23
	Mean 8.22	8.22

* *Ammonium salt of 2:4-Dinitrophenol**

The behaviour of this salt towards thorium is similar to that of ammonium picrate. On the addition of the reagent in the cold, however, thorium is partially precipitated which becomes complete only on heating over a boiling water-bath. Precipitation,

* The ammonium salt of 2:4-dinitrophenol was prepared by repeated evaporation of 2:4-dinitrophenol with silica-free ammonia on a water-bath and crystallisation of the product twice from water.

washing and recovery of adherent thorium are carried out in the same manner as with ammonium picrate. Results of test estimations, of separations and of estimations of thorium in monazite are shown in Tables IV, V and VI respectively.

TABLE IV
Estimation of thorium.

No.	ThO ₂ taken.	ThO ₂ weighed.		Total.
		Major fraction.	Minor fraction.	
1	0.0696 g. 0.0696	0.0678 g. 0.0680	0.0017 g. 0.0016	0.0695 g. 0.0696
3	0.0348	0.0334	0.0014	0.0348
4	0.0348	0.0332	0.0014	0.0346

TABLE V
Separation of thorium from cerite earths.

No.	ThO ₂ taken.	R ₂ O ₃ added.	ThO ₂ obtained.	Diff.
1	0.0656 g.	0.0740 g.	0.0696 g.	...
2	0.0696	0.1480	0.0698	+0.2 mg.
3	0.0348	0.1480	0.0347	-0.1
4	0.0348	0.2220	0.0359	+0.2
5	0.0348	0.2960	0.0348	..
6	0.0348	0.3700	0.0346	-0.2

TABLE VI
Estimation of thorium in monazite.

Wt. of sample.	% ThO ₂ obtained.	
	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid.	Ammonium salt of 2:4-dinitrophenol.
1.0024 g.	8.24	...
0.9940	8.20	...
0.8478	...	8.18
0.9170	...	8.24
0.8010	...	8.23
0.7850	...	8.26
		Mean 8.23

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
ANDHRA UNIVERSITY,
WALTAIR.

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